

Juvenile and the Abuse

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ABSTRACT

Recent studies have revealed common risk factors for adolescent drug abuse and delinquency. The relationship between substance abuse and juvenile delinquency sketches a bleak portrait of juvenile justice system overwhelmed by drug and alcohol abusing and addicted 10 – to -17- years old. Juvenile crime is one of the nation’s serious problems. Government policy on juvenile delinquency must often struggle with the balance of concern over the healthy developments of children and adolescents who violate the law and public desire to punish the criminals. Nevertheless, children and adolescents who commit criminal acts must be educated and supported in a growth process. A number of cognitive and social features of childhood and adolescence influence the context of juvenile crime policy. They were likely to have been neglected and abuse by parents. Many had grown up in impoverished and dangerous neighborhoods. Schools, teachers, and administrators had been unable to engage them. The provider’s had failed to diagnose their problems. It further gives the high rate of drug use among delinquents, drug-abuse intervention and treatment programs clearly needed for delinquent populations. This paper explores the linking about adolescent drug use and delinquency, distinguishing factors, implications for preventions and treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Juvenile crime is one of the serious problems. Concern about it is widely shared by government officials and by public. State began to take tougher legislative stance towards juvenile. Young people begin to experiment with drugs, new social groups, music and their sexuality from the age of 14. Many will explore new ideas, have challenging times with their parents and other authority figures and may begin to act out. In the majority of cases, this is key

stage in growing up. A young person who is engage in dangerous drinking and drug –taking are placing themselves and others at higher risk. The use of drugs during adolescence can cause significant physical and social problems that can endure. As a young people is going through a distinct period of change, being involved in drugs and drug culture can change the body chemistry, cause harm to sensitive brain cells and even the development of mental health issues such as anxiety and depression. And due to different thought processes , they will experiment in dangerous and risky ways and will also involve in anti-social activities, become the victims of crime. Being involve in this can have long lasting effects on a person’s life. The main response to the most recent spike in violent juvenile crime has been enactment of laws and distinction between juvenile courts and adult courts. The rehabilitative model embodied in the Juvenile Justice and Delinquency Prevention Act of 1974, focusing on the needs of the young offender. To deal with young offenders requires knowledge of factors in the individual , family, social settings, and community that influence the development of delinquent behaviour , types of offenses committed by young people , and the types of interventions that can most effeciently and effectively prevent offending or its recurrence.

Definition of Juvenile ?

According to the new law, age of juvenile for both male and female involved in conflict with law has been fixed at 18 years. Under Juvenile Justice Act, 2000 is “ a juvenile who is alleged to have committed an offence but has not completed 18 years of age on the date of commission of said offence”. And under the Juvenile Justice Act 2015 juvenile defined under section 2(35),”juvenile means a child below the age of eighteen years”.

Delinquency Defined?

Delinquency is a term that is used to describe illegal or antisocial behaviour and activities. "Delinquency consisted of socially unaccepted acts". Delinquent behaviour may include drug use, underage drinking, violence, sex crimes or property crimes. Individuals who are delinquent typically express antisocial opinions, are involved in activities that are dangerous, harmful and wrong and are often outspoken in their rejection of punishments associated with their crimes. The first ever legislation on juvenile delinquency, passed by the State of Illinois in 1899 which specifies various specific kinds of delinquency in addition to the offences covered by the criminal laws.

Juvenile delinquency declared variety of acts which are described as below:-

Immoral or offensive conduct, Knowingly associating with immoral persons, Visiting houses of bad reputation, Visiting liquor shops, Roaming in street in night, Engaging in illegal and unlawful business, Violation of any law of state, Immoral conduct in school, Habitually wandering on roads, Driving without license, Habitually bunking from schools, Incorrigible, Habitually using immoral language in Public Place, Running away from home without permission, Smoking at public places, Begging or receiving alms.

Gibbons defines "Juvenile Delinquency consists of acts or infractions which are prohibited in statutes of individual states".¹

Drug Use And Delinquency :-

Understanding causes of juveniles turning towards drug abuse :

There are numerous causes of teenage drug abuse, each of which can contribute to a life-long habit of consuming drugs, alcohol and cigarettes.

- Lack of Supervision – Teenagers who are left alone for long period of time will have more opportunities for exposure to drugs.
- Availability- If retailers sell alcohol and cigarettes to minors, they are contributing to the problem.

- Lack of Communication- Many of the causes of teen drug abuse can be eliminated simply by talking.
- Running with wrong crowd- Children who are involved with wrongdoers also often fall into bad habits.
- Lack of spiritual grounding- Rarely attending religious services are linked to higher risk for substance abuse and delinquency.

Dangerous effects of drug use in juveniles:

- Drugs of any kind decreases teen's ability to pay attention.
- They are more likely to relapse into drug abuse when trying to quit.
- They are more likely to have unprotected sex.
- Substance may cause other emotional problems like anxiety, depression, .
- Substances of abuse can effect virtually everyone of the body's system. Eg- heart attack, halted breathing.
- Substance abusing youth may be alienated from and stigmatized by their peers.
- Psychological disorders.²

Consequences of youth substance abuse

- Academics- declining grades, absenteeism from school and other activities, dropping out of school.
- Physical health- physical disabilities, effects of possible overdoses
- Mental health- depression, development lags, apathy, attempted suicide.
- Peers- alienated from the stigmatized by their peers.
- Families- abuse of alcohol and other drugs by youth may result in family crises and jeopardize many aspects of family life.
- Social and economic consequences- They result from financial losses and distress.

Preventing Drug Abuse in Juveniles

Delaying use of psychoactive drugs, alcohol, and tobacco among adolescents is a critical, national, and public health goal. Often a formal intervention is necessary to convince the substance abuser to submit to any form of treatment. Behavioral interventions and

¹ <http://ijtsrd.org/index.php/journal/problem-of-drug-abuse-in-juvenileeffects-and-remedies/>

² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3734705>

medications exist that have helped many people reduce, or discontinue, their substance abuse.

Some of the following preventing techniques and treatment to stop drug abuse in juveniles could prove to be helpful:-

- Central role of parents
- National Youth Anti-Drug Media Campaign
- Safe and Drug-Free Schools And Communities
- Youth Awareness programs for Education
- Reducing the drug availability
- Efficient law enforcement machinery
- Stringent penalties
- Compulsory treatment of addicts

Preventive Programmes

The 2010 NIDA Report emphasizes both the role of family and community preventive programmes as vital to deterring child and adolescent substance abuse.

Family preventive programme- The NIDA Report emphasize that the following family characteristics place children at a higher risk for substance abuse, parents with a habit of alcoholism and drug abuse, high level of family conflict, lack of inconsistent people.

Multi-dimensional family therapy(MDFT) It is family based partial hospitalization programme for substance abusing adolescents. It focuses on helping youth develop more effective coping and problem solving skills for better decision making and helps the family to improve interpersonal functioning as a protective factor.

Reconnecting Youth- A school based prevention programme for high school students with poor school achievement and a potential for not completing their education. The programme goals are to increase school performance, reduce drug use, and learn skills to manage mood and emotions.

Role of healthcare providers in prevention- It is believed that less than 30 percent of primary care providers perform any screening for substance abuse

and as many as 69 percent do not offer any type of counselling.³

CONCLUSION

The abuse is a substantial amount of evidence-based research available to physicians, community of alcohol and drugs has resulted in significant morbidity and mortality among adolescents worldwide. Many of these youth will lose their lives to drugs and alcohol and a significant number are likely to grow up to become problem drug users. Although, the substance abuse problem is complex and large in magnitude, there leaders and schools to implement interventions that can decrease adolescent substance abuse rates. Because this issue is not peculiar to any one community or culture, we recognize that individual interventions may not be universally effective. Therefore, we emphasize the NIDA strategy of targeting modifiable risk factors and enhancing protective factors through family, school and community prevention programmes, as a generalized framework for healthcare and community activists to use when researching programmes and strategies best suited for their own community.

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³ National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA) A research-based guide for parents, educators and community leaders. 2nd ed. Bethesda, Maryland, USA: NIDA; 2010. Preventing drug use among children and adolescents.